

CPT inverted dark sector predicts current Hubble constant

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Abstract

A unified theory of particle and gravitational physics should preserve charge-parity-time (CPT) symmetry while explaining astronomical observations attributed to hypothetical dark matter and dark energy. To meet these objectives a new quantum charge is hypothesized, associated with a particle's time sense. Normal matter particles have $U = +1$. Dark matter particles have $U = -1$, interact with advanced rather than retarded electromagnetic and gravitational waves, and undergo cosmic "contraction" rather than cosmic "expansion." The symmetrized Einstein field equations become bimetric to support the two sectors. We identify a cosmic reference frame where physical laws are manifestly CPT symmetric, matter distribution is assumed CPT symmetric around some space-time point, and cosmic scale factors manifest as a fundamental scalar field coupled to Planck's constant and the Higgs mechanism. Predicted baryon acoustic oscillation observations have a form already shown by Fulvio Melia to be exceptionally consistent with astronomical observations. From the current normal matter Higgs field self-coupling parameter λ , we infer the symmetry time redshift, z_S . From this and the astronomically observed physical cosmic microwave background and baryon densities, we infer the Hubble constant. Our numerical results are $z_S = 0.668 \pm 0.001$ and $H_0 = 71.07 \pm 0.25$ (km/s)/Mpc.

Keywords: particle physics, general relativity, gravitational waves, dark matter, cosmological models, Hubble constant, fundamental constants, natural units, neutrinos

1. Introduction

1.1 A puzzle

It has long been a puzzle as to how the time-symmetric nature of known microscopic physical laws can be consistent with the perceived unidirectional flow of time, the observation of retarded but not advanced electromagnetic and gravitational waves, and the expansion but not contraction of the universe. See for example the work of J. V. Narlikar [1]. Here we suggest that the universe is indeed more time symmetric than is apparent.

1.2 A particle physics hypothesis

We hypothesize a new quantum number that determines whether a particle behaves with a normal or reversed time sense. We call this new quantum number *kuuk* charge after an Inuit word for river, intending to invoke an image of the flow of time, with potential values of 1, -1, and perhaps 0. We associate $U = 1$ with the conventional time flow, and $U = -1$ with the opposite flow.

This new kuuk sector is somewhat like Lee and Yang's suggestion of reestablishing overall parity symmetry by postulating a sector of opposite-handedness particles [2]. However, we extend the concept of spatial inversion to space-time inversion. F. R. Stannard has already proposed such a sector, calling it "Faustian," although he seems to have focused on nongravitational implications [3] [4].

Each U sector interacts with what its observers see as retarded interactions. No nongravitational interactions between kuuk and normal matter are assumed here. Thus kuuk matter appears virtually dark to a normal matter observer and normal matter appears virtually dark to a kuuk matter observer.

Introduction of this new quantum number forces reconsideration of the definitions of charge-parity-time (CPT) symmetry and antimatter. Technically one defines "antimatter" to require that all fundamental particle quantum charges be reversed, so one might call kuuk matter "true" antimatter since everyday antimatter lacks kuuk charge reversal from normal matter. Thus, it is normal and kuuk matter that exchange under the CPT symmetry of our extension of the Standard Model of particle physics.

1.3 Implications for gravity

We apply gravitational theory with minimum extensions. We assume that all matter is attractive. To a Newtonian approximation the gravitation of all particles is the same. This is consistent with the behavior claimed for hypothetical dark matter.

We extend Einstein Field Equations (EFE) to include kuuk matter by an application of what might be called "the inverse quantum correspondence principle." A bi-metric theory somewhat like S. Hossenfelder's Bi-Metric Theory with Exchange Symmetry [5] is needed to support the kuuk sector's advanced gravitational waves and cosmic contraction.

$$G_{U\mu\nu} = \kappa_E T_{U\mu\nu} + \kappa_E T_{-U\mu\nu} \quad (1.2.1)$$

The Greek letter κ_E is used to denote Einstein's gravitational constant, and the Latin U is used to denote the normal or kuuk sector.

Here one metric represents the spacetime seen by normal matter and radiation while the other represents the spacetime seen by kuuk matter and radiation. Both EFE have right-hand sides consisting of the sum of normal and kuuk matter stress-energy tensors. The normal stress-energy tensor supports normal time-sense nongravitational physics while the kuuk stress-energy tensor represents reverse time-sense nongravitational physics. The normal stress-energy tensor excites retarded gravitational waves in the normal metric while the kuuk stress-energy tensor excites advanced gravitational waves in the kuuk metric. Similarly, the normal metric "expands" under the influence of the universe's matter while the kuuk metric "contracts" since we select oppositely signed square roots in the Friedmann equation solutions. Thus the symmetrized EFE are CPT symmetric, removing the symmetry breaking that occurs with the original EFE due to selection of only retarded waves and only a positive square root in the Friedmann equation.

We further assume that the universe is cosmologically CPT symmetric, a hypothesis previously put forward by A. D. Sakharov [6]; that is, the cosmic spacetime distribution of matter and radiation is CPT symmetric about some spacetime point, x_S . We also note that Hoyle and Narlikar put forward a similar concept [7]. The matter in the spatial slice at the cosmic symmetry time, t_S , has CP symmetry about the space symmetry point x_S ; CPT symmetric laws then guarantee CPT symmetry of the distribution over time. Note that in what follows we will continue to use the Latin letter S in subscripts to denote values at the symmetry time.

We may consider the universe before the symmetry time as the CPT mirror of the universe after the symmetry time. Here we may also alternatively consider the kuuk sector to be the CPT-reversed image of the normal sector superimposed on the normal sector and stretching infinitely back and forward in time.

We emphasize, however, that we do *not* assume that the space-time symmetry point is that of the Big Bang singularity but find that t_S is much more recent. We make no assumption about the spatial location of the symmetry point; it might be

located outside our current cosmological horizon. We note also that there could be countably infinite space-time symmetry points if the spatial distribution of matter has a crystalline structure at the symmetry time, so we are not requiring that the universe has a spatial center.

One might suppose that symmetry between normal and kuuk matter particles is inconsistent with kuuk matter being the usual hypothetical astronomical dark matter, since that matter is thought to have about five times the mass density of normal matter [8] [9]. However, we will show here that, due to gravitational particle mass effects, kuuk matter accounts for virtually all the hypothetical dark matter *and* dark energy driving current normal sector cosmic “expansion.”

1.4 Contents of remaining sections

In the Methods section we focus on the cosmology problem, developing a kuuk model of cosmology that can be quantitatively compared with the concordance Lambda-CDM model [8] [9] in the Results section. The concordance model postulates dark energy (either a cosmological constant Lambda, or a more complex variant), spatial curvature that may or may not be zero, and some sort of cold dark matter in addition to normal matter and radiation. In our kuuk cosmological model we postulate no cosmological constant, no spatial curvature, and a dark sector consisting only of kuuk matter and radiation that is CPT symmetric with normal matter and radiation. In the first part of the Methods, we develop the classical theory with a symmetrized Friedmann equation and in the second part of the Methods section we apply the quantum correspondence principle to infer a quantum mechanical mechanization of the classical cosmology.

In the Results section we fix the redshift of the cosmic symmetry time by using particle physics data and then use the symmetrized Friedmann equation to predict the current Hubble constant.

In the Discussion section we compare our prediction of the Hubble constant with other work. We then discuss the symmetry of the cosmic entropy of our model and how it relates to the second law of thermodynamics and the past hypothesis. Finally, we discuss our results from a Euclidean quantum field theory viewpoint and establish appropriate natural units for further study.

In the Conclusion section we summarize and make suggestions for further work on neutrinos.

2. Methods

2.1 Symmetric Friedmann Equation

2.1.1 Naïve symmetrization. A bi-metric Friedmann-Lamaitre-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) metric provides a classical description of the concurrent cosmic “expansion” that is associated with normal matter and the cosmic “contraction” that is associated with kuuk matter. Common spatial coordinates are achieved by using comoving coordinates.

We start by writing down the normal matter Friedmann equation [10] for the case with no cosmological constant and no spatial curvature and the usual scale factor a , normalized at the current epoch.

$$\left(\frac{da}{dt}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G \rho a^2}{3} \quad (2.1.1)$$

Then we rewrite this as a symmetrized bimetric Friedmann equation, consistent with Eq. 1.2.1, in terms of a symmetrized scale factor, Q , normalized to unity at the postulated symmetry time t_s .

$$\left(\frac{dQ_U}{dt}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G \rho Q_U^2}{3} = \frac{8\pi G (\rho_U + \rho_{-U}) Q_U^2}{3} \quad (2.1.2)$$

Where the symmetric scale factors are defined as follows:

$$Q_U(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{a_U(t)}{a_U(t_s)} \quad (2.1.3)$$

The symmetry between the sectors requires their scale factors satisfy the following:

$$Q_U(t) = \frac{1}{Q_{-U}(t)} \quad (2.1.4)$$

We then follow the usual practice of expressing cosmic mass densities in terms of critical density fractions, but at the time of symmetry rather than at the current epoch.

$$\rho(Q) = \rho_S (\Omega_{SRU} Q_U^{-4} + \Omega_{SBU} Q_U^{-3} + \Omega_{SB-U} Q_{-U}^{-3} + \Omega_{SR-U} Q_{-U}^{-4}) \quad (2.1.5)$$

The subscript S continues to denote symmetry time, the subscript R denotes radiation, and the subscript B denotes baryonic matter. Here we have neglected neutrino mass.

By considering the CP symmetry at the symmetry time, zero spatial curvature, and Eq. 2.1.4, we can rewrite Eq. 2.1.5 with only one unknown critical density fraction and with only one sector’s scaling scalar.

$$\rho(Q) = \rho_S \left(\left(\frac{1}{2} - \Omega_{SB} \right) (Q\bar{U}^{-4} + Q\bar{U}^4) + (\Omega_{SB})(Q\bar{U}^{-3} + Q\bar{U}^3) \right) \quad (2.1.6)$$

Thus, *three* parameters are needed to define the kuuk cosmology--for example, the total mass density at the symmetry time, the baryonic mass density at the symmetry time, and the value of the symmetric scale factor at the current epoch.

This result can be compared with the similar expression from Lambda-CDM cosmology, which may include the total mass density at the current epoch, 5 critical fractions, plus a dark energy equation of state parameter [8].

$$\rho_{LCDM}(a) = \rho_0 (\Omega_R a^{-4} + (\Omega_C + \Omega_B) a^{-3} + \Omega_k a^{-2} + \Omega_\Lambda a^{-3(1+w)}) \quad (2.1.7)$$

If we assume, which may be justified by observational data, that the curvature term is zero and that the state equation parameter is the default of -1, then *four* parameters are still required to define the LCDM cosmology. For example, these parameters may be the physical densities at the current epoch for radiation, baryonic matter, cold dark matter, and dark energy.

There are, however, two problems with this symmetric Friedmann equation as it would usually be interpreted. First, it does not appear to fit astronomical observations such as determination of the Hubble constant variation with redshift from baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO) observations. Second, it does not appear to manifest the energy conservation which we desire for a successful integration with particle physics. The solution to both problems is the same.

2.1.2 Enforcing conservation of cosmic energy. These difficulties can be resolved by supplementary conditions enforcing energy conservation. This is reasonable since here we are considering all radiation and matter in the universe, not just that of the normal sector. Therefore, we require that the cosmic energy density is constant:

$$\rho(Q) c(Q)^2 = constant \quad (2.1.8)$$

This implies a dependence of the speed of light on scale factor

$$c(Q)^2 = \frac{c_S^2 \rho_S}{\rho(Q)} \quad (2.1.9)$$

When introducing a variable speed of light into physical theory it is important to also specify how other physical constants may be impacted, as pointed out by G. F. R. Ellis [11]. Here we seek to extend current gravitation theory as minimally

as possible, so we insist that the Einstein gravitational constant remains a true constant.

$$\kappa_E = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = constant \quad (2.1.10)$$

Therefore a second condition, which makes the Newton gravitational “constant” a function of scale factor, follows from Eq. 2.1.9 and Eq. 2.1.10.

$$G(Q) = G_S \frac{c(Q)^4}{c_S^4} = G_S \frac{\rho_S^2}{\rho(Q)^2} \quad (2.1.11)$$

Note that $\rho(Q)$, $c(Q)$, and $G(Q)$ are all even functions about the symmetry time.

We may still use the symmetrized Friedmann Eq. 2.1.2 (together with Eq. 2.1.5 or Eq. 2.1.6), but with the understanding that the supplementary condition Eq. 2.1.11 is used to make Newton’s gravitational constant variable, and that the speed of light has also become variable, according to supplementary Eq. 2.1.9.

Alternatively, we may rewrite our symmetric equation assuming these conservation of energy conditions, using Eq. 2.1.2, Eq. 2.1.9, Eq. 2.1.11, and Eq. 2.1.10 to get a form using Einstein’s gravitational constant and variable speed of light.

$$\left(\frac{dQ_U}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{\kappa_E \rho_S c_S^2 Q_U^2 c(Q)^2}{3} \quad (2.1.12)$$

By applying the definition of Hubble constant, $H = \dot{a}/a = \dot{Q}/Q$, we may conclude from Eq. 2.1.12 that

$$\frac{H(Q)}{c(Q)} = \frac{H_0}{c_0} = constant \quad (2.1.13)$$

Where the 0 subscript denotes evaluation at the current epoch.

Equivalently, we divide Eq. 2.1.12 through by $c(Q)^2$ and transform to the spatial variable, using $dx/dt = c(Q)$.

$$\left(\frac{dQ_U}{dx} \right)^2 = \frac{\kappa_E \rho_S c_S^2 Q_U^2}{3} \quad (2.1.14)$$

Note that the right-hand side makes the symmetric scale factors exponential functions of distance from the symmetry space-time point.

Eq. 2.1.13 allows successful prediction of the Hubble constant observations made with the “standard ruler” of Baryon

Acoustic Oscillations (BAO), as we shall show in the Discussion section.

2.2 Quantum interpretation of Friedmann equation

2.2.1 Variable particle mass. We next apply the quantum correspondence principle to our symmetric Friedmann equation mass density, Eq. 2.1.5, to find implications for particle physics. We interpret the scale factors as a fundamental scalar field rather than as simultaneous geometric expansion and contraction. The log function of this scalar field also defines time for both sectors in a common Minkowski frame (albeit with an underlying time-varying speed of light). We interpret the factors in Eq. 2.1.5 as telling us how normal and kuuk particle properties change with this scalar field in their common comoving frame. We generalize work done by F. Hoyle and J. V. Narlikar where they recast the Einstein-De Sitter model into the Minkowski metric with variable particle mass [7]. Our approach also falls within the general class of reformulations advocated by L. Lombriser [12].

Thus we interpret the baryon terms of the symmetric Friedmann equation to mean that normal and kuuk particle masses scale as follows:

$$m_U = m_S Q_U^{-3} \quad (2.2.1)$$

Eq. 2.2.1 and Eq. 2.1.4 imply that the masses of particles in the different sectors scale in the opposite way--normal particles become lighter while kuuk particles become heavier with increasing normal time.

Similarly, we interpret the radiation terms in the symmetric Friedmann equation to describe how a free photon's effective mass (energy/ c^2) changes. Here we assume free photons maintain their frequency in the Minkowski frame. This implies that the ratio of the Planck constant to speed of light squared must become a function of scale factor, with opposite scaling depending on whether the photon is normal or kuuk. Thus,

$$\frac{\hbar_U(Q)}{c(Q)^2} = \frac{\hbar_S}{c_S^2} Q_U^{-4} \quad (2.2.2)$$

These relations are consistent with observers seeing cosmic redshift of distant astronomical objects. Note that the ratio of Eq. 2.2.1 and Eq. 2.2.2 scale as the first power of Q_U . Hoyle and Narlikar showed that, when the ratio mc^2/\hbar (they "absorbed" the \hbar and c in their notation) scales with the first power of the scale factor scalar, observers will see cosmic redshift [7]. By considering variation in Planck's constant as well as particle mass, our approach provides a mechanism for the origin of

CMBR like that of the LCDM model, overcoming a past concern with Hoyle and Narlikar's work [10].

There is still a problem with the scaling of photon energy and massive particle energy seen in the Friedmann equation. If the Planck's constant scales with the fourth power, then the Standard Model would require that the massive particles also scale with the fourth power. However, the symmetric Friedmann equation implies the massive particles scale with the *third* power (Eq. 2.2.1).

2.2.2 Higgs coupling to cosmic scale factor. The Standard Model must be extended to make it consistent with the cosmic scaling for particle masses. A simple solution is to couple the scale factor scalar with the Higgs field.

We start from the usual form of the Higgs potential [13]:

$$V(\phi) = \mu^2(\phi^\dagger\phi) - \lambda(\phi^\dagger\phi)^2 \quad (2.2.3)$$

We then symmetrize this and couple the scale factor scalar to the Higgs field as follows:

$$\phi_U \leftarrow Q_U^{-1}\phi_U \quad (2.2.4)$$

$$V(\phi_U) = \mu_S^2 Q_U^{-2}(\phi_U^\dagger\phi_U) - \lambda_S Q_U^{-4}(\phi_U^\dagger\phi_U)^2 \quad (2.2.5)$$

Finally, we assume based on considerations of symmetry and simplicity that $\lambda_S = 1$. Then we get the following simple equation, valid over cosmic time.

$$V(\phi_U) = \phi_S^2 Q_U^{-2}(\phi_U^\dagger\phi_U) - Q_U^{-4}(\phi_U^\dagger\phi_U)^2 \quad (2.2.6)$$

An observer at any epoch will measure

$$\mu_U^2 = \phi_S^2 Q_U^{-2} \quad (2.2.7)$$

$$\lambda_U = Q_U^{-4} \quad (2.2.8)$$

This extension provides the required additional power of particle mass scaling. Eq. 2.2.7 and Eq. 2.2.8 imply that the coupling factor for fermion mass, v , has become cosmic scale factor dependent.

$$v_U(Q) = \left(\frac{\mu_U^2}{\lambda_U}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{\mu_S^2}{\lambda_S} Q_U^2\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = v_S Q_U \quad (2.2.9)$$

We note that the mass of the Higgs boson itself has an opposite scaling change from other particles.

$$m_{HU} = (2\mu_U^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} = (2\phi_S^2 Q_U^{-2})^{1/2} = m_{HS} Q_U^{-1} \quad (2.2.10)$$

Since the value of the Higgs self-coupling parameter has become a dynamic value, we can measure it to determine the current value of the symmetric cosmic scale factor:

$$Q_U = \lambda(Q)_U^{-1/4} \quad (2.2.11)$$

This completes our application of the correspondence principle to our symmetric Friedmann equation.

3. Results

3.1 Redshift of the symmetry time t_s

We now apply the method described above to the current epoch. We start by finding the redshift of the cosmic symmetry point using particle physics data. Large Hadron Collider (LHC) data tells us that the Higgs boson mass is 125.22 ± 0.11 GeV/ c^2 [14]. Using a value of 246.220 GeV/ c^2 for the Higgs field [14], based on the highly accurate knowledge of the Fermi constant, allows us to estimate the value of the Higgs self-coupling parameter at this epoch as

$$\lambda_0 = 0.12928 \pm 0.00023 \quad (3.1.1)$$

It then follows from Eq. 2.2.11, Eq. 2.1.3 and the redshift equation, $z + 1 = 1/a$, that

$$Q_0 = 1.66770 \pm 0.00073 \quad (3.1.2)$$

$$a_S = 0.59963 \pm 0.00026 \quad (3.1.3)$$

$$z_S = 0.66770 \pm 0.00073 \quad (3.1.4)$$

Thus, the time of cosmic symmetry is relatively recent.

3.2 Current Hubble constant

With the redshift of the symmetry time in hand we can use the method of Section 2.1 to predict the current Hubble constant from normal sector conditions in the current epoch. Two additional physical densities are needed to achieve the three parameters needed to define the kuuk cosmology. Recommended values for cosmic microwave background radiation (CMBR) and baryon physical densities are given by the Particle Data Group in their Table 2.1, Astrophysical Constants and Parameters [14].

$$\Omega_{0R} h_0^2 = 0.00002473 \pm 0.00000001 \quad (3.2.1)$$

$$\Omega_{0B} h_0^2 = 0.02237 \pm 0.00015 \quad (3.2.2)$$

Where h_0 is the Hubble constant in units of 100 km/s/Mpc.

Using the definition of critical fractions at the current epoch and Eq. 2.1.5 and Eq. 2.1.6, we can say that

$$\frac{\Omega_{0R}}{\Omega_{0B}} = \frac{(1/2 - \Omega_{SB})Q^{-4}}{\Omega_{SB}Q^{-3}} \quad (3.2.3)$$

Solving this for Ω_{SB} , we get

$$\Omega_{SB} = \frac{\Omega_{0B}}{2\Omega_{0R}} \frac{Q^{-4}}{Q_0^{-3} + \frac{\Omega_{0B}}{\Omega_{0R}} Q_0^{-4}} \quad (3.2.4)$$

We can also say that

$$\Omega_{0B} = \frac{\Omega_{SB} Q_0^{-3}}{(\frac{1}{2} - \Omega_{SB})(Q_0^{-4} + Q_0^4) + (\Omega_{SB})(Q_0^{-3} + Q_0^3)} \quad (3.2.5)$$

Using the definition h_0 , we can infer the following:

$$H_0 = 100 \sqrt{\frac{\Omega_{0B} h_0^2}{\Omega_{0B}}} \quad (3.2.6)$$

Using the values in Eq. 3.1.2, Eq. 3.2.1 and Eq. 3.2.2, we can compute the following:

$$\Omega_{SB} = 0.4990799 \pm 0.0000061 \quad (3.2.7)$$

$$\Omega_{0B} = 0.04428 \pm 0.00011 \quad (3.2.8)$$

$$H_0 = 71.07 \pm 0.25 \text{ ((km/s)/Mcp)} \quad (3.2.9)$$

Note that we can also use Eq. 2.1.9 and Eq. 2.1.6 to determine how much the speed of light has changed since the symmetry time.

$$\frac{c_0}{c_S} = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_S}{\rho_0}} = 0.64154 \pm 0.00038 \quad (3.2.10)$$

$$\frac{c_S}{c_0} = 1.55874 \pm 0.00093 \quad (3.2.11)$$

4. Discussion

4.1 H_0 agreement

Our prediction for the current Hubble parameter, Eq. 3.2.9, is consistent with the range of local determinations of the Hubble constant that have been put forward recently. For example, our prediction lies between the values recently given by A. G. Riess et al [15], 73.2 +/-0.9 (km/s)/Mpc; and W. L. Freedman et al [16], 69.96 +/- 0.9 (statistical) +/-1.12 (systematic) (km/s)/Mpc.

However, our prediction is in strong tension with the Planck collaboration's value, 67.4 +/-0.5(km/s)/Mpc, which is based on assuming the LCDM model and projecting forward from Planck satellite CMBR measurements [9]. The tension is to be expected since both predictions have better than 1% precision but are based on different cosmological models.

If our model is correct then future determinations of the local Hubble constant should coalesce around our value, with possible adjustments for improved knowledge of Higgs self-coupling value and the physical density of normal baryonic matter. Note that the normal baryonic matter estimate may shift if one uses the physics discussed here when deriving estimates from observational data. Likewise, the Planck satellite-based prediction may also shift if one uses the kuuk cosmology model physics in the required analysis.

4.2 Baryon acoustic oscillations agreement

Going beyond predictions of the current Hubble constant, we can validate the kuuk model's Hubble constant predictions over the period since the release of the CMBR by examining astronomical observations of baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO), i.e., the frozen variations in matter density that are remnants of early cosmic baryon-photon fluid oscillations.

The basic measurements associated with using the BAO standard ruler, r_d , to measure the history of the Hubble "constant" are measurements of variation in redshift along the line-of-sight and measurements of angle in the transverse direction, Δz and $\Delta\theta$. The predicted measurements follow from Eq. 2.1.13 and the fact that in the comoving frame the scale of the BAO remains constant.

$$\Delta z = \frac{r_d H(Q)}{c(Q)} = \frac{r_d H_0}{c_0} \quad (4.2.1)$$

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{r_d}{\int_0^z \frac{c(z')dz'}{H(z')(1+z')}} = \frac{r_d H_0}{c_0 \ln(1+z)} \quad (4.2.2)$$

Rather than compare this result with observational data, we instead compare it to the BAO measurements predicted by the $R_h = ct$ model studied extensively by F. Melia [17] [18]. His model assumes a cosmic state equation with "no active mass," but is not specific about the constituents that allow this.

$$\rho^{rhct} c^2 + 3p^{rhct} = 0 \quad (4.2.3)$$

Melia has described his prediction for BAO measurements [19]. He gives two distance measures, which we convert to measurement predictions using his formulas.

$$d_H^{rhct}(z) = \frac{c}{H_0(1+z)} \quad (4.2.4)$$

$$d_M^{rhct}(z) = \frac{c}{H_0} \ln(1+z) \quad (4.2.5)$$

$$\Delta z^{rhct} = \frac{r_d}{(1+z)d_H^{rhct}(z)} = \frac{r_d H_0}{c} \quad (4.2.6)$$

$$\Delta\theta^{rhct} = \frac{r_d}{d_M^{rhct}(z)} = \frac{r_d H_0}{c \ln(1+z)} \quad (4.2.7)$$

If we compare Eq. 4.2.1 and Eq. 4.2.2 to Eq. 4.2.6 and Eq. 4.2.7, we see that the predictions are the same, although Melia does not subscript c since he assumes it to be a constant. Surely his value for c was measured in the current cosmic epoch.

Melia has made extensive studies of how well his model fits astronomical data. The subset of those studies that are of BAO are directly applicable to validating our model since the predictions are the same. He has found that in general his model fits the BAO observations better than LCDM [19]. Thus we may reach the same conclusion about our model's ability to fit BAO observations relative to LCDM.

Melia also argues that attempts to fit an LCDM model to a universe that actually meets his cosmic state equation must result in mass and dark energy densities like those being reported for LCDM models [20], thus explaining how LCDM can still fit the data to some accuracy.

Here we have presented a specific physical hypothesis about the constituents of the universe that leads to behavior in at least some ways identical to Melia's model. Our model appears to differ from Melia's model in that we predict a variable speed of light but whether this is a true physical difference or only some difference in how the same physics is represented remains to be determined. We do provide more specificity in that we are able to predict the value of H_0 .

4.3 Cosmic thermodynamics symmetry

The second law of thermodynamics suggests a unidirectional arrow of time. Attempts have been made to achieve consistency with otherwise CPT symmetric physical laws by invoking an

initial condition of extremely low entropy (at the Big Bang), the so-called “past hypothesis” [21].

If we examine entropy of the universe that has kuuk cosmology, then the isolated system of the second law must include both the normal and kuuk sectors. The cosmic entropy is found to be minimum at the symmetry time, increasing symmetrically with time measured relative to symmetry time. The second law no longer provides a cosmic unidirectional arrow of time, but rather sector level and opposing arrows of time. One may replace the past hypothesis and the corresponding “future hypothesis” with a hypothesis of cosmic CP symmetry at the symmetry time.

4.4 Euclidean quantum field theory viewpoint

P. Woit has suggested that “one should take as fundamental four-dimensional quantum field theory in the Euclidean signature” [22]. It appears to us that quantum Euclidean field theory [23] does apply here. The symmetric cosmic scale factor plays a fundamental role and appears to have the character that one might expect for a quantum scalar native to the Euclidean realm. It has an exponential dependence on the time-associated x_μ variable (Eq. 2.1.14), as do Euclidean quantum field Green’s functions. This also implies that this x_μ variable should be considered more fundamental than the t variable, since the effects of the variable speed of light are suppressed, revealing the fundamental dynamics of the scalar field. Also, the cosmic scale factor scalar’s dependence on the average cosmic energy density suggests that it may be truly nonlocal, which T. Nakano identified at the birth of Euclidean quantum field theory as a characteristic available in native defined Euclidean quantum fields [24].

The space-time symmetry point here plays a role reminiscent of the zero and time direction selection appearing in the Osterwalder and Schrader theorem. Above we considered one solution to be positively exponential over all time and one to be negatively exponential over all time. However, from the Euclidean quantum field theory viewpoint, solutions should be even about the symmetry time, where one increases exponentially with time away from the symmetry time and the other decreases exponentially with time away from the symmetry time. We could then assemble the solutions we have been using from halves of these Euclidean field theory solutions.

We wonder whether Woit could extend his concepts for a unified theory of particle physics and gravity to include the kuuk sector described here. This might then make spacetime ambidextrous, rather than just “right-handed” as in his current concept [25].

4.5 Cosmological units

Finally, we discuss the implications of this work for systems of units. For a single epoch and sector one may continue to work in Planck units, which until now have been considered natural units [26]. However, all the constants upon which Planck’s units are based, G , \hbar , and c , have now become dynamic rather than constant. Furthermore, units will differ between the normal and kuuk sectors since the value of their Planck constants diverge away from the symmetry time. Thus Planck units do not achieve the universality for all time, space, and observers that was the original goal of Planck [27].

To develop natural units for our situation we follow the method of F. Wilczek [28], first considering fundamental constants and then constructing units. We define five cosmological fundamental constants as follows:

$$\kappa_{8\pi} (\text{M}^{-1}\text{L}^{-1}\text{T}^2) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\kappa_E}{8\pi} = \frac{G}{c^4} \quad (4.5.1)$$

$$\hbar_{c2S} (\text{MT}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar_U \hbar_{-U}}{c^2 c^2}} = \frac{\hbar_K}{c^2} \lambda_U^{-1} \quad (4.5.2)$$

$$c_S (\text{LT}^{-1}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{H_{US} c}{H_U} = H_{US} \left(\frac{dz}{dx} \right)^{-1} = \frac{H_{US} \lambda_U^{-\frac{1}{4}} c}{d\lambda_U^{-\frac{1}{4}}/dt} \quad (4.5.3)$$

$$m_{eS} (\text{M}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{m_{eU} m_{e-U}} = m_{eU} \lambda_U^{-3/4} \quad (4.5.4)$$

$$\varepsilon_{c2} (\text{M}^{-1}\text{L}^{-5}\text{T}^6\text{I}^2) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\varepsilon_{vac}}{c^2} = \frac{\varepsilon_S}{c_S^2} = \frac{\varepsilon_0}{c_0^2} \quad (4.5.5)$$

Here we have given each constant’s dimension for reference in parentheses after its symbol.

The first constant is a renormalization of Einstein’s gravitational constant, which has been considered a fundamental constant since Einstein’s development of the general theory of relativity. The second is related to Planck’s constant but has become symmetrized under our theory and is related to the Planck “constants” that are observed in the normal and kuuk sectors. This new constant can be determined within a given sector by measuring the current Planck “constant,” current speed of light, and current value of the Higgs self-coupling parameter. (See the equations developed in the methods section, especially Eq. 2.2.2 and Eq 2.2.8.)

The third constant is the speed of light at the symmetry time; see especially Eq. 2.1.13. We give an estimate for the value of this constant in our Eq. 3.1.11. Determining c_S through purely local experiments appears problematic. The value we give is based on estimates of cosmic CMBR and baryonic matter

density. In Eq 4.5.3 we give several formulas based on assuming that the Hubble constant at the symmetry time is known. The constant can then be determined either by measuring the current Hubble constant and current speed of light, by measuring the spatial derivative of cosmic redshift, or by measuring the Higgs self-coupling “constant” and its time derivative. (However, directly measuring this time derivative is obviously beyond current technology.)

The fourth constant is the mass of the electron at the symmetry time. The fifth constant is related to the permittivity of the vacuum at the symmetry time but accounts for the variable speed of light.

We can construct natural units by taking an appropriate subset of these constants. Here we first construct *cosmic Planck (CP) units*, which turn out to be equal to regular Planck units evaluated at the symmetry time. CP units achieve universality for all time, space, and observers, meeting Planck’s original goal. But note also that the Planck time unit does not scale only with the cosmic redshift, but also by a factor related to the variable speed of light.

$$t_{CP} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{\hbar_{c2S} \kappa_{8\pi} c_S} = \lambda_U^{-1/2} \left(\frac{H_{US}}{H_U} \right)^{1/2} t_P \quad (4.5.6)$$

$$m_{CP} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar_{c2S}}{\kappa_{8\pi} c_S}} = \lambda_U^{-1/2} \left(\frac{H_{US}}{H_U} \right)^{-1/2} m_P \quad (4.5.7)$$

$$l_{CP} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{\hbar_{c2S} \kappa_{8\pi} c_S^3} = \lambda_U^{-1/2} \left(\frac{H_{US}}{H_U} \right)^{3/2} l_P \quad (4.5.8)$$

We can also construct a cosmic version of “particle and atomic physics” (PA) units based on c, m_e, \hbar , and ϵ [26]; we designate these cosmic units CPA. Note that the scaling between the PA time unit and the CPA time unit is the cosmic redshift, making these units more appropriate when considering remote optical atomic emissions.

$$t_{CPA} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\hbar_{c2S}}{m_{eS}} = \lambda_U^{-1/4} \frac{\hbar_U}{m_{eU} c_U^2} = \lambda_U^{-1/4} t_{PA} \quad (4.5.9)$$

$$m_{CPA} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} m_{eS} = \lambda_U^{-3/4} m_{eU} = \lambda_U^{-3/4} m_{PA} \quad (4.5.10)$$

$$l_{CPA} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\hbar_{c2S} c_S}{m_{eS}} = \lambda_U^{-1/4} \frac{H_{US}}{H_U} \frac{\hbar_U}{m_{eU} c_U} = \lambda_U^{-1/4} \frac{H_{US}}{H_U} l_{PA} \quad (4.5.11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} e_{CPA} &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sqrt{\epsilon_{c2} \hbar_{c2S} c_S^5} = \lambda_U^{-1/2} \left(\frac{H_{US}}{H_U} \right)^{5/2} \sqrt{\epsilon \hbar_U c} \\ &= \lambda_U^{-1/2} \left(\frac{H_{US}}{H_U} \right)^{5/2} e_{PA} \end{aligned} \quad (4.5.12)$$

Note that we can also construct cosmic length, time, and mass units that avoid the issue of determining c_S by selecting $\kappa_{8\pi}, \hbar_{c2S}$, and m_{eS} as our base constants.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Summary

We have put forward a novel quantum number capturing a particle’s or field’s intrinsic time sense. This quantum number, combined with symmetry principles, allows the definition of a highly constrained dark sector that quantitatively explains the cosmic expansion effects attributed to dark matter and dark energy.

Our hypothesis enables a CPT symmetric description of the universe allowing a more unified theory of gravity and particle physics. It identifies cosmic coordinates, physical constants, scalar quantum fields, couplings, and natural units that make the CPT symmetry manifest. It also explains how cosmic energy conservation occurs through energy flow between the normal and kuuk sectors as the scale factor scalar changes.

Our approach to cosmology starts with two copies of general relativity and particle physics and casts the theory into the Minkowski metric, thus placing all the dynamics on the right-hand side of the EFE. The two copies of the physics there may imply some connection to the perturbative duality between gauge theory and gravity hypothesized in so-called double copy theory [29]. However, we are not aware that dual time senses play an explicit role in double copy theory.

The highly entangled state of the cosmos at the cosmic symmetry time is a three-dimensional artifact reminiscent of the sought-after cosmic hologram [30]. Perhaps we look through a hologram when we make optical and gravitational wave observations of events with redshift greater than z_S .

We have used the LHC in a novel way, as the largest clock ever made, and the only one that measures cosmic time.

5.2 Future work

Although we have postulated no non-gravitational interactions between normal and kuuk matter, neutrinos should be studied for reverse time sense, as suggested by J. V. Narlikar [31]. The observed mass eigenstates of neutrinos might for example have $U = 1, 0$, and -1 . If we make this assumption, then

neutrino oscillation data have approximately 3.5 power cosmological scaling for neutrino masses. However, we have not worked out whether there is theoretical justification for such a claim.

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